

First-principles Study in the Electronic Structure of Carbon-doped Hexagonal Boron Nitride

Altaf Mujear^{1*}, Li Hui¹, Yang Zhi¹, Wang Zhu²

¹ College of Physics, Taiyuan University of Technology, Taiyuan 030024, Shanxi Province

² Hubei Key Laboratory of Radiation Chemistry and Functional Materials, School of Nuclear Technology and Chemistry & Biology, Hubei University of Science and Technology, Xianning 437100, China

Abstract: Identifying the defects reveals vital information about the electrical and physical properties of the materials. It might be difficult to define defects in h-BN due to its intricate microstructure. Therefore, the peculiarities of the h-BN defects must be addressed. Impurities are anticipated to be a major factor in defect chemistry because of the high formation energies of native point defects. In this paper, we have studied the structural and electronic properties of carbon impurity defects in h-BN by first-principles calculations based on the generalized gradient approximation method in the density functional theory (DFT). We calculated the formation energies of substitution C on the B site (C_B), substitution C in the nitrogen site (C_N), the complex defects of B vacancy with substitution C on the B site ($V_B C_B$), and the N vacancy with substitution C in nitrogen site ($V_N C_N$) in different charge states under both N-rich and N-poor growth conditions. Our results show that the stable charge states of C_B defect has reasonably low formation energies under both N-rich and N-poor conditions. The stable charge states of C_N defects are more stable under the N-poor condition. Complex defects appear with high formation energies under both N-rich and N-poor conditions. According to the obtained results, the neutral, +1, and +2 charge states of C_B are very stable under N-rich conditions with values of 1.54, -1.39, and -1.53 eV, respectively. Under N-poor conditions, the +1 and +2 charge states of C_B and the neutral and +1 charge states of C_N defect are the most stable defects with values of 1.17, 1.02, 1.55, and 1.37 eV, respectively. The results also show that under the N-rich condition, the $V_N C_N^{-3}$ has the highest formation energy (20.55 eV), and under the N-poor condition the $V_B C_B^{-3}$ has the highest formation energy with a value of 18.67 eV. The rest of the charge state defects have values between 1.37 eV and 20.55 eV under both N-rich and N-poor growth conditions.

Keywords: Carbon-doped in h-BN, h-BN, Formation energy, Defect in h-BN

*Corresponding Author: Altaf Mujear

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Introduction

Growing research interest in h-BN has resulted from the development of growth techniques for its monolayer, multilayer, and single-crystal forms[1, 2]. Because of its structural similarity to graphene but different electronic

properties, h-BN has a wide band gap (the optical band gap of h-BN is found at 6.08 eV)[3], strong radiation resistance, and good lattice matching with graphene. Hexagonal boron nitride has an isoelectronic structure close to graphite. h-BN is an sp^2 bonded planar van der Waals material. It is an important electronic device material, especially in solid-state neutron radiation detectors in recent years[4]. It also has a good application prospect. h-BN is a wide-band gap semiconductor that can be employed in far-ultraviolet light-emitting diodes[5, 6], in contrast to semimetal graphite. Semiconductor material defects have a significant impact on the performance of semiconductor devices and have always been a key concern in the field of semiconductor material research. Characterizing h-BN defects might be challenging. Therefore, it is crucial to go over the characteristics of h-BN defects. The use of first principles is of great significance for the study of defects in h-BN[7-11].

Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) is getting a lot of attention for two-dimensional electronics and as a host for single photon emitters[12, 13]. Numerous factors could have an impact on how materials grow throughout production. Determining the appropriate characteristics and environmental factors is therefore essential. Previous studies have reported that due to their large formation energies, native vacancy and antisite defects in h-BN are rare to occur under thermodynamic equilibrium under the usual growth conditions[12]. And they report that, most likely, defects involving carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen impurities dominate the defect chemistry of h-BN. Low-energy defects in h-BN include substitutional carbon and oxygen, interstitial hydrogen, and boron vacancy-hydrogen complexes. According to their results, they rule out a number of potential sources for defect-related luminescence in h-BN. They specifically discover that the frequently seen 4.1 eV emission cannot be connected to recombination at C_N , contrary to what has previously been thought. They offer alternate hypotheses for the sources of this emission, including C_B as a potential candidate. In this study, our results also show that substitutional carbon defects have a reasonably low formation energy while complex defects of substitutional carbon with native vacancy of both boron and nitrogen have a high formation energy.

Experiments on the systemization of single-layer BN have revealed several defects (like vacancies[14]) and impurities (like carbon[15]). It has been shown that vacancies and the C impurity have a significant impact on BN-based materials' luminescence[16, 17]. To further optimize BN's optical properties[18, 19], it is crucial to have an in-depth understanding of the characteristics of these defects and impurities. Additionally, because BN and graphene have comparable atomic structures, attempts have been undertaken to generate hybrid BNC structures by substitutionally doping C in BN structures during growth or post-synthesis[20-22]. BNC sheet has garnered a lot of interest mostly because of its adjustable band gap achieved by adjusting the relative concentration of C and BN. For graphene, h-BN makes an excellent gate-insulating layer. Since h-BN has a high surface optical phonon energy, employing it as the substrate is probably going to improve the performance of graphene devices under situations like greater temperatures and a stronger electric field[23]. Understanding the defect characteristics of C-doped BN is crucial for further experimentation doping process optimization.

Based on the first principles calculation by using density functional theory within the generalized kohn-Sham scheme, this paper calculated the defects formation energies and defects energy levels of carbon-doped defects such as substitution C on the B site (C_B), substitution C on the N site (C_N) defects and complex defects such as B vacancy with substitution C on the B site defect ($V_B C_B$) and N vacancy with substitution C on the N site defects ($V_N C_N$) within different charge states under both N-rich and N-poor conditions, and analyzed the stability of these defects in h-BN. The research results obtained contribute to the systematic understanding of the nature of defects in h-BN.

Research Methodology

Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN)

Research interest in h-BN has grown as monolayer, multilayer, and single-crystal growth have become more common. This material is also a strong candidate for use in two-dimensional electronics in conjunction with graphene due to their similar structural makeup but dissimilar electronic properties[24]. For these applications, h-BN's solidity and structural

integrity are essential. h-BN is a semiconductor with a wide bandgap that can be employed in far-ultraviolet light-emitting, in contrast to semimetal graphite. More information about properties of h-BN will be presented in the results section (subsection3.1).

Fig. 1: (a) The view of the optimized bulk honeycomb structure of 128 of h-BN, green and grey colors represent boron and nitrogen atoms, respectively. (b) Top view of the optimized bulk h-BN mono-layered spacing and AA'-type stacking sequence

Computational details

Within the generalized Kohn-Sham scheme, density functional theory was used for our calculations. Utilized was the Vienna ab initio simulation package's (VASP) plane-wave pseudo-potential code[25]. The exchange correlation potential was calculated using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) method within the generalized gradient approximations (GGA) to represent the core-electron interaction. We considered a supercell with 128 atoms in total. 500 eV was chosen as the plane-wave cut-off energy, and the Brillouin zone was sampled using $5 \times 5 \times 3$ Gamma-centered Grids from Monkhorst-Pack. Forces on all relaxed atoms were less than 0.02 eV/Å, and the energy convergence criteria were 10^{-6} per unit cell. During structure optimization, spin polarization was taken into consideration. The optB88-vdW correction approach was used to account for the impact of Van de Waals interactions.

Fig. 2: Figures (a) and (b) are the plane layer view of substitution C on the B site C_B and substitution C on the N site C_N defects in h-BN in the z-axis, respectively. The brown color refers to carbon, while the dark blue and green refer to B and N atoms, respectively

Defect formation energies calculation

Based on calculations of total energy, we evaluate defect formation energies and transition levels using the commonly used approaches[12]. The defect formation energy of a defect D in charge state q within the supercell formalism for the modeling of defects in a host lattice is defined as

$$E_f[D; q] = E_{tot}[D; q] - E_{tot}[h - BN; 0] - \sum_i n_i \mu_i + q(\epsilon_f + E_{VBM}) \quad (1)$$

where $E_f[D; q]$ is the formation energy of a defect D in charge state q; The $E_{tot}[D; q]$ and $E_{tot}[h - BN; 0]$ are the total energies of the supercells with and without (bulk) defects, respectively. n_i stands for the number of atoms of type i that are either added ($n > 0$) to the supercell or deleted ($n < 0$) from the supercell. The chemical potentials of different atomic

species, μ_i , which characterize particle exchange with respective reservoirs. In semiconductors, the Fermi energy ϵ_f is found between the valence band maximum (VBM) and conduction band minimum (CBM). Here no finite size correction is included.

Based on equation 1, the dopant can exist in different charge states such as neutral ($q = 0$), remove electron or more than electrons ($q = +$), or add electron or more than electrons ($q = -$) charge states. Equation 1 shows that the formation energy of the charge-neutral dopant $q = 0$ is independent of the Fermi level, and the formation energies of the other charged defects are dependent on the Fermi level. Additionally, each charged defect may have the lowest formation energy within a specific ϵ_f range. Therefore, the Fermi level value at which two charged states q and q' have equal formation energies $E_f(D; q; \epsilon_f = 0) = E_f(D; q'; \epsilon_f = 0)$ may be used to determine the charge transition level of a dopant, which can be expressed as

$$\epsilon(q/q') = \frac{E_f(D; q; \epsilon_f = 0) - E_f(D; q'; \epsilon_f = 0)}{q' - q} \quad (2)$$

where $E_f(D; q; \epsilon_f = 0)$ is the formation energy of defect with charge state q when the Fermi level is at the VBM ($\epsilon_f = 0$).

Chemical potentials

The experimental conditions can be represented by the chemical potentials μ_i , i refers to native boron B and nitrogen N atoms, or extrinsic carbon C atoms. The B and N atoms' chemical potentials vary within a range determined by the corresponding BN bulk structure's heat of formation, which is specified as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{BN} - \mu_B(\text{bulk}) - \mu_N(\text{bulk}) \\ = H_{BN} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where μ_{BN} and H_{BN} denote the chemical potential and the formation enthalpy of bulk hexagonal boron nitride, respectively. $\mu_B(\text{bulk})$ denotes the chemical potential of a single atom in solid-phase B, and $\mu_N(\text{bulk})$ denotes the chemical potential of an N atom;

The thermodynamic equilibrium growth of h-BN is ensured by the condition

$$\begin{aligned} &\mu_{BN} \\ = &\mu_B \\ + &\mu_N \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, N-rich condition identify to,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_N \\ = &\mu_N(\text{bulk}) \\ \mu_B = &\mu_{BN} - \mu_N \\ = &\mu_B(\text{bulk}) + H_{BN} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

And N-poor condition identify to,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B \\ = &\mu_B(\text{bulk}) \\ \mu_N = &\mu_{BN} - \mu_B \\ = &\mu_N(\text{bulk}) + H_{BN} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Computational details

Density functional theory (DFT) was used for all of the calculations in the generalized Kohn-Sham scheme. The plane-wave pseudo-potential code in the Vienna ab-initio simulation package (VASP) was employed. The core-electron interaction was modeled using the projector augmented wave (PAW) formalism, and the exchange-correlation potential was calculated using the Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE)) technique under generalized gradient approximations

(GGA). Using periodic boundary conditions, all structures were addressed within 128 atoms supercell geometry, substitution C in the boron site (C_B) defect is formed by replacing a carbon atom with a boron atom, substitution C in the nitrogen site (C_N) defect is performed by replacing a carbon atom with the nitrogen atom, the $V_B C_B$ is a complex defect created by removing boron atom from the supercell and replacing carbon with boron atom, and $V_N C_N$ is a complex defect formed by removing nitrogen atom and replacing carbon with nitrogen. $5 \times 5 \times 3$ Gamma-centered Monkhorst-Pack grids were used to sample the Brillouin zone with cut-off energy for plane waves of 500 eV. The energy of all relaxed atom forces was less than 0.02. The required energy convergence was 10^{-6} per unit cell. Spin polarization was taken into account during structural optimization. Van der Waals interactions were taken into consideration using the optB88-vdW correction method.

Fig. 3: (a) A view of complex defects of B vacancy with substitution C on the B site defect ($V_B C_B$) in h-BN in the z-axis. (b) The plane layer view of N vacancy with substitution C on the N site defects ($V_N C_N$) in h-BN in the z-axis. The brown color refers to carbon, while the dark blue and green refer to B and N atoms, respectively

Results

Bulk properties of h-BN

The optimized 128 bulk h-BN structure and mono-layer view of h-BN are depicted in figures 1a and 1b, respectively. The reported crystal structure of h-BN with the crystal's symmetry has a space group hexagonal, $P\bar{6}m2$, and a point group D_{6h} is used, we get 128 atoms by the $4 \times 4 \times 2$ transformation matrix. The h-BN stacks in a AA'-type. In the plane, each boron atom is threefold coordinated to nitrogen, and that of nitrogen, generating a honeycomb structure in Sp^2 bonding. The computed in-plane B-N bond length is 1.45 Å, which is consistent with the value that was previously published. The computed lattice parameters are $c = 6.581$ Å, $c/a = 2.63$ Å, these values are in line with the experimental values[26], and the computed distance between the two layers is 4.14 Å. Finally, the PBE-calculated band gap of h-BN is 4.26 eV[27].

Formation energies results

We calculated the formation energies of the substitution C in the boron site (C_B) defect, substitution C in the nitrogen site (C_N) defect, the complex defect of boron vacancy combined with substitution C in the boron site C_B defect ($V_B C_B$), and the complex defect of nitrogen vacancy combined with substitution C in the nitrogen site C_N defect ($V_N C_N$) in charge states that go from -3 to +3, in order to make sure that we take into consideration every possible transition levels. Figures 4a and 4b show the formation energies of stable defect of the substitution C in the boron site (C_B) defect under both N-rich and N-poor, respectively. Figures 4c and 4d despotic the formation energies of stable defect of the substitution C in the nitrogen site (C_N) defect under both N-rich and N-poor, respectively. Figures 5a and 5b give the formation energies of stable defect of the complex defect of boron vacancy with substitution C in the boron site ($V_B C_B$) defect under both N-rich and N-poor, respectively. Figures 5a and 5b show the formation energies of stable defect of

the complex defect of nitrogen-vacancy with substitution C in the nitrogen site ($V_N C_N$) defect under both N-rich and N-poor, respectively. Table (1) presents all presented defects formation energies (E_f) in h-BN under both N-rich and N-poor conditions with stable charge state q when the Fermi level is at the VBM ($\epsilon_f = 0$) and shows the bond length of the first neighbor of the stable charge state of both C_B and C_N . Figure 6 shows the charge-state transition levels of C_B , C_N , $V_B C_B$ and $V_N C_N$ defects in h-BN.

Table 1: Carbon-doped defects formation energies (E_f) in h-BN under both N-rich and N-poor conditions with stable charge state q when the Fermi level is at the VBM ($\epsilon_f = 0$) and the bond length of the first neighbor of the stable charge state of both C_B and C_N

Vacancy	Charge state	$E_f(N - rich)$ eV	$E_f(N - poor)$ eV	Bond length of first neighbor B-N at the vacancy(\AA)
C_B	-1	5.69	8.24	1.454
	0	1.54	4.09	1.461
	+1	-1.39	1.17	1.378
	+2	-1.53	1.02	1.378
C_N	-2	9.68	7.13	1.466
	-1	5.50	2.95	1.466
	0	4.10	1.55	1.443
	+1	3.92	1.37	1.437
$V_B C_B$	-3	13.57	18.67	
	-2	9.68	14.79	
	-1	6.58	11.68	
	0	5.28	10.39	
$V_N C_N$	-3	20.55	15.44	
	-2	16.54	11.44	
	-1	12.88	7.78	
	0	9.55	4.45	
	+1	8.96	3.86	

Substitution C in the boron site (C_B)

Here we investigate C substitution at the boron site (C_B) (figure 2a). The formation energies results show that neutral, -1,+1, and +2 charge states are stable with three transition levels (2+/1+) level of 0.15 eV, (1+/0) level of 2.93 eV, and (0/1-) level of 4.14 eV above the VBM (figure 6). The formation energy of the neutral charge state of C substitution at the boron site, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 1.54 eV under the N-rich condition and 4.09 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1). The formation energy of the -1 charge state of C substitution at the boron site, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 5.69 eV under the N-rich condition and 8.24 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1). The formation energy of the +1 charge state of C_B , when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is -1.39 eV under the N-rich condition the negative value of formation energy indicates that the C_B^{+1} is nonmagnetic[7], and under the N-poor condition the formation energy of C_B^{+1} is found to be 1.17 eV (table 1). For the +2 charge state, the formation energies are -1.52 eV and 1.02 eV under N-rich and N-poor, respectively (table 1). The C_B^{+2} is also nonmagnetic. The formation energies of these stable charge states are plotted under both N-rich and N-poor conditions in figures 4a and 4b, respectively. As we can see from these results, the C_B in different charge states have low formation energy that can be considered as a stable defect. The C_B defect is very likely to exist experimentally.

These results are in good agreement with other studies[12, 28]. The bond length of the first neighbor of the stable charge state of both C_B are presented in table 1.

Substitution C in the nitrogen site (C_N)

For C substitution at the nitrogen site (C_N) (figure 2b). From the charge states transition levels (figure 6), we can find that the neutral, -2, -1, and +1 charge states are stable with three transition levels (1+/0) level of 0.18 eV, (0/1-) level

Fig. 4: (a) and (b) are the formation energies of stable charge states of C_B defects in h-BN as a function of Fermi level under N-rich conditions and N-poor conditions, respectively. (c) and (d) are the formation energies of stable charge states of C_N defects in h-BN as a function of Fermi level under N-rich conditions and N-poor conditions, respectively

of 1.40 eV, and (1-/2-) level of 4.17 eV above the VBM. The formation energy of the neutral charge state, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 4.1 eV under the N-rich condition and 1.55 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1), for C_N^{-2} , the formation energy, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 9.68 eV under the N-rich condition and 7.13 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1), for C_N^{-1} , the formation energy is 5.5 eV under the N-rich condition and 2.95 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1), and for C_N^{+1} , the formation energy, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 3.92 eV under the N-rich condition and 1.37 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1). Figures 4c and 4d show the formation energy as a function of Fermi level for the stable charge states of C substitution at the nitrogen site (C_N) under both N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively. We can see that C_N is more stable under the N-poor condition, under the N-rich condition the most stable charge state is +1 while the -2 charge state has reasonably high formation energy which means that it is unlikely to exist experimentally. Under N-poor conditions, except the -2 charge state, all -1, 0, and +1 have low formation energies, these defects are very likely for experimental research. Comparing C_N to C_B , C_B is more stable under both N-rich and N-poor conditions with a high formation energy of -1 charge state under N-poor condition with a value 8.24 eV when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, while C_N has somehow high formation energies unser N-rich condition and has low formation energy under the N-poor condition except for -2 charge state which has a high formation energy under both N-rich and N-poor conditions. These results are in line with the previous studies[12, 28]. The bond length of the first neighbor of the stable charge state of both C_N are presented in table 1.

Complex defect ($V_B C_B$)

Complex defect $V_B C_B$ (figure 3a) has four stable charge states, the neutral, -3, -2, and -1 with three transition levels (0/1-) level of 1.29 eV, (1-/2-) level of 3.1 eV, and (2-/3-) level of 3.89 eV above the VBM (figure 6). The formation energies of these stable charge states of Complex defect $V_B C_B$ have very high formation energies under both N-rich and N-poor conditions, the most stable charge state defect is with the neutral charge state under N-rich conditions, the formation energy of neutral complex defect $V_B C_B$, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 5.28 eV under the N-rich condition and 10.39 eV under the N-poor condition (table 1), for $V_B C_B^{-3}$, the formation energy, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 13.57 eV under the N-rich condition and 18.67 eV under the N-poor (table 1), about $V_B C_B^{-2}$, the formation energy, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 9.68 eV under the N-rich condition and 14.79 eV under the N-poor (table 1). Finally, the $V_B C_B^{-1}$, the formation energy, when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum, is 6.58 eV under the N-rich condition and 11.68 eV under the N-poor (table 1). Figures 5a and 5b show the formation energy as a function of Fermi level for the stable charge states of complex defect $V_B C_B$ under both N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively. Generally, the complex defect $V_B C_B$ has very high formation energies with the different charge states, it is clear that these defects are not likely to exist experimentally. The only neutral charge state of complex defect $V_B C_B$ is the stables defects under the N-rich condition.

Fig. 5: (a) and (b) are the formation energies of stable charge states of $V_B C_B$ defects in h-BN as a function of Fermi level under N-rich conditions and N-poor conditions, respectively. (c) and (d) are the formation energies of stable charge states of $V_N C_N$ defects in h-BN as a function of Fermi level under N-rich conditions and N-poor conditions, respectively

Complex defect ($V_N C_N$)

Complex defect $V_N C_N$ (figure 3b) has four stable charge states, the neutral, -3, -2, -1, and +1 with four transition levels (1+/0) level of 0.59 eV, (0/1-) level of 3.33 eV, (1-/2-) level of 3.65 eV, and (2-/3-) level of 4.01 eV above the VBM (figure 6). The formation energies of these stable charge states of Complex defect $V_N C_N$ have the highest formation energies specifically under both N-rich condition, under the N-poor condition still also has high formation energies for -3, -2, and -1 while neutral and +1 charge states have low formation energies. the calculated formation energies when the Fermi level is at the valance band maximum are as follows, for $V_N C_N^{-3}$, the formation energies are 20.55 eV and 15.44 eV under N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively (table 1). For $V_N C_N^{-2}$, the formation energies are 16.54 eV

and 11.44 eV under N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively (table 1). $V_N C_N^{-1}$, the formation energies are 12.88 eV and 7.78 eV under N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively (table 1). $V_N C_N^0$, the formation energies are 9.55 eV and 4.45 eV under N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively (table 1). $V_N C_N^+$, the formation energies are 8.96 eV and 3.86 eV under N-rich and N-poor conditions, respectively (table 1). We plot the formation energies of the stable defects of $V_N C_N$ as a function of Fermi level under N-rich condition (figure 5c) and under N-poor condition (figure 5d). To sum up, our results show that the complex defect $V_N C_N$ has extremely high formation energies under both N-rich and N-poor conditions, and only two charge states (neutral and +1) have low formation energy under the N-poor condition.

Fig. 6: The charge-state transition levels of C_B , C_N , $V_B C_B$, and $V_N C_N$ defects in h-BN

Conclusion

We employ density functional theory with the Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) technique to characterize carbon-doped defects in h-BN. By studying different types of carbon-doped defects in h-BN (Substitution C in the boron site C_B , Substitution C in the nitrogen site C_N , Complex defect $V_B C_B$, and Complex defect $V_N C_N$) in different charge states under both N-rich and N-poor, this study revealed defect structures and their physical properties. Following is an overview of the conclusions: In the N-rich conditions, results in table 1 show that C_B has reasonably low formation energies specifically with neutral, +1, and +2 charge states with values 1.54 eV, -1.39 eV, and -1.53 eV, respectively. The results also show that both C_B^{+1} and C_B^{+2} are nonmagnetic materials under the N-rich condition as a result of negative formation energies. And the $V_N C_N$ defect has the highest formation energies with a value of 20.55 eV of $V_N C_N^{-3}$. In the N-poor conditions, the results show that C_B has the lowest formation energies with a +1 charge state of 1.17 eV and a +2 charge state of 1.02 eV. And it is also clear that both the neutral charge state and +1 charge state of C_N has low formation energies. The highest formation energy appears with $V_B C_B^{-3}$ with a value of 15.44 eV.

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